

A Tracer Study of 2012-2019 Graduates from Bachelor of Science in Business Administration at Cotabato City State Polytechnic College, Philippines

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Abstract: This study was conducted to trace the Cotabato City State Polytechnic College (CCSPC)-College of Business and Public Administration (CBPA) graduates in terms of their educational background, employment opportunity, and contribution of curricular program to their communication, human relations, leadership and problem solving skills. Moreover, this study was conducted in CCSPC, Sinsuat Avenue, Cotabato City. The respondents were the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration from year 2012 to 2019 and they were selected using purposive and convenience sampling. It employed quantitative research and utilized descriptive-status research design. The statistical tools used were frequency, percentage, and mean. The results revealed that majority of the respondents are single, female, and graduates of BSBA major in Marketing Management. For their employment opportunity, majority of them have been employed and in a regular or permanent employment status. In addition, they are commonly connected with these industry classifications: wholesale/trade, government, and banking and finance. The results also revealed that the curricular program contributed to the development of their communication, human relation, leadership and problem solving skills.

Keywords: *curricular program, communication, human relation, leadership and problem solving skills*

I. Introduction

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) is an institution created to oversee the higher education system in the country. Moreover, this agency is also mandated to: oversee graduates that are both locally and globally responsive and competitive; promote quality standards of higher education that is accessible and affordable for all. It is further reinforced by the Executive Order No. 83 series of 2012 that establishes the Philippines Qualification Framework which mandates the Department of Education (DepEd), Commission on Higher Education (CHED), Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), Philippine Regulatory Commission (PRC), and Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) to review the learning standards in basic education, technical skills development and higher education.

In order to assess the effective and ineffective components of a specific program or project, the commonly used assessment instrument is the tracer study. According to Millington (2001) tracer study is a quantitative structural data that explores the professional track and experiences of the graduates. Thus, it is imperative to conduct this study particularly in the College of Business and Public Administration (CBPA) for the following reasons: it is the first to be conducted to evaluate the old implemented curriculum; to provide appropriate and relevant information particularly on the employability and employment experiences of the graduates; to serve as the basis for curriculum development; and to comply with one of the required documents by any higher education accrediting body.

II. Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to trace the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration from year 2012-2019.

Specifically, it answered the following queries:

1. What is the general information of the graduates in terms of their:
 - a. Civil Status
 - b. Sex
 - c. Age
2. What is the educational background of the respondents in terms of their:
 - a. Bachelor's Degree
 - b. Year Graduated
 - c. Reasons for taking the course or pursuing the degree
 - d. Continuing Professional Education
 - e. Professional Examination Passed
3. What is the employment data of the respondents?
 - a. Employment Opportunity
 - b. Reasons for Unemployment
 - c. Present Employment Status
 - d. Industry Classification of Company
 - e. Place of Present Work
 - f. First job after college
 - g. Reasons for staying the job
 - h. Relationship of the course to the first job
4. What is the extent of the curricular program contribution to the development of the graduates' skills in terms of their:
 - a. Communication Skills
 - b. Human Relations Skills
 - c. Leadership Skills
 - d. Problem Solving Skills

III. Significance of the Study

The results of the study are found to be beneficial to the school administrators for it can provide evidence-based recommendations to improve the graduates' employability. Moreover, the program heads can benefit from the results of this study because it can serve as the ground basis for curriculum review, re-engineering, and development. In the same manner, the faculty can use it as a guide to plan activities that are up-to-date and relevant to enhance the

graduates' knowledge, skills, and attitudes in order to meet the demands of the society and industry. On the other hand, the students, alumni officers, and future researchers can take advantage from the results of this study by fostering professional networking, coaching, and career path planning.

IV. Research Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive research design because it describes a certain population and situation particularly the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration in Cotabato City State Polytechnic College. Specifically, descriptive-status was used in this study because it determines the educational background of the respondents; their employment data; and extent of curricular program contribution to their communication, human relations, leadership, and problem-solving skills.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the graduates of the College of Business and Public Administration particularly under the program of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration from year 2012-2019. A total of 154 respondents participated in this research. **Research Locale**

This study was conducted in Cotabato City particularly in Cotabato City State Polytechnic College, Sinsuat Avenue, Cotabato City.

Research Instrument

A modified research instrument was used in this study. A survey questionnaire was designed to answer the research problems. Part I is the profile characteristics of the respondents; Part II is the educational background of the respondents; Part III provides information on the employment status of the respondents; and lastly Part IV provides information on the extent of curricular program contributions to graduates skills particularly communication, human relations, leadership, and problem-solving. This survey questionnaire was also subjected to validity and reliability tests.

Response Anchor		
Range	Description	Interpretation
1.0-1.85	Strongly Disagree	Curricular program did not strongly contributed to the development of graduates' skills
1.86-2.7	Disagree	Curricular program did not contributed to the development of graduates' skills
2.71-3.55	Disagree to some extent	Curricular program did not contributed to some extent to the development of graduates' skills
3.56-4.4	Neutral	Curricular program neither contributed to the development of graduates' skills
4.45-5.25	Agree to some extent	Curricular program contributed to some extent to the development of graduates' skills
5.26-6.10	Agree	Curricular program contributed to the development of graduates' skills
6.11-7.0	Strongly Agree	Curricular program strongly contributed to the development of graduates' skills

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers requested the participation of the graduates through different media such as email, facebook, texts, and phone calls. Majority of the respondents were contacted during the CCSPC Alumni Election. However, there were also respondents who provided their responses through online particularly the google form. It was a cross-sectional survey and the methods of administering were face-to-face survey and online survey.

Sampling Technique

Non-random sampling technique was used in this study specifically purposive sampling technique and convenience sampling technique. It was purposive because those graduates of the College of Business and Public Administration under the program of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration were selected. Moreover, it was convenience sampling technique because respondents were reached out through online and during the CCSPC alumni election.

Statistical Tool

The following descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data gathered from the respondents: frequency, percentage, and mean. The profile of the respondents was analyzed using the frequency and percentage and this goes with the analysis of the respondents’ educational background and employment status. The extent of curricular program contribution to graduates’ skills was analyzed using the mean.

Ethical Consideration

In the conduct of this research, the objectives of the research were fully explained to the respondents. They were requested to answer the survey questionnaire and they were not forced in any ways. It is further explained that any responses gathered from them were treated with utmost objectivity.

V. Presentation and Analysis of Results

Table 1. General Information of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their civil status, sex and age. It clearly shows that majority of the respondents are single with 84.4%. Moreover, more than half of the respondents are female with 63%. And in terms of their age, 40.9 percent belongs to the age bracket of 24-26 years old while 27.3% and 25.3% belongs to age brackets 21-23 years old and 27-29 years old respectively.

Civil Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	130	84.4
Married	24	15.6
Total	154	100.0
Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	57	37.0
Female	97	63.0
Total	154	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percent
below 21 years old	4	2.6
21-23 years old	42	27.3
24-26 years old	63	40.9
27-29 years old	39	25.3
more than 30 years old	6	3.9
Total	154	100.0

Table 2. Educational Background of the Respondents

Table 2.1 Bachelor’s Degree

Table 2.1 depicts the characteristics of the respondents in terms of their graduated bachelor’s degree. It is clearly shown that almost all of the respondents were graduates of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management with 94.8% while the remaining 5.2% were graduates of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Human Resource Development Management.

Bachelor’s Degree	Frequency	Percent
BSBA Major in Marketing Management	146	94.8
BSBA Major in HRDM	8	5.2
Total	154	100.0

Table 2.2 Year Graduated

Table 2.2 indicates the respondents' year of graduation which varies from year 2012-2019. Out of 154 respondents 31 of them graduated in year 2019; 30 of them in year 2014; 26 of them in year 2017; and 11 of them in year 2012.

Year	Frequency	Percent
2012	11	7.1
2013	13	8.4
2014	30	19.5
2015	17	11.0
2016	16	10.4
2017	26	16.9
2018	10	6.5
2019	31	20.1
Total	154	100.0

Table 2.3 Reasons for taking the course or pursuing the degree.

Table 2.3 shows the reasons of the respondents in taking the course or pursuing the degree. The common reasons of the respondents were affordable tuition fee, prospect for better employment, school location, and availability of course offering in CCSPC.

Reasons	Frequency
Affordable Tuition Fee	84
Prospect for better employment	69
School Location	55
Availability of course offering in CCSPC	55
Prospect for career advancement	54
Personal prestige of being enrolled in CCSPC	43
Availability of scholarship	37

Table 2.4 Continuing Professional Education

Table 2.4 reflects the continuing professional education of the respondents. It is evident that almost all of the respondents did not continue professional higher education with 92.8%. However, there were graduates who pursued Master in Public Administration with 3.2%; Master in Business Administration with 2.0%; and Bachelor of Science in Education with 2.0%.

Professional Education	Frequency	Percent
None	143	92.8
MPA	5	3.2
MBA	3	2.0
BSED	3	2.0
Total	154	100.0

Table 2.5 Professional Examination Passed

Table 2.5 represents the professional examinations passed by the respondents. As can be seen, almost all of the respondents didn't pass any professional examination although based on the follow-up interview conducted; almost all of them had taken the Civil Service Professional Examination. On the other hand, minimal percentage was accounted for the Civil Service Professional Examination with 5.8%; PNP Examination with 1.3%; and Licensure Examination for Teachers with 1.3%

Professional Examination Passed	Frequency	Percent
None	140	90.9
Civil Service Professional Examination	9	5.8
PNP Examination	2	1.3
LET	2	1.3
Fire	1	.6
Total	154	100.0

Table 3. Employment Data

Table 3.1 Employment Opportunity

Table 3.1 shows the employment opportunity of the respondents. It is clearly shown that majority of the respondents have been employed with 87.7%. On the other hand, there are also respondents who said that they have never been employed after graduation and this accounts to 12.3%.

Employment Opportunity	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	135	87.7
Never been employed	19	12.3
Total	154	100

Table 3.2 Reasons for Unemployment

Table 3.2 depicts the reasons of the 19 respondents who have no history of employment after graduation. Nine (9) of them responded that lack of work experience is the main reason why they are still unemployed with 47.9%. Other reasons are few job vacancies with the 36.8% followed by difficulty of passing the pre-employment interview with 10.5%.

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of work experience	9	47.4%
Few job vacancies	7	36.8%
Mismatch of educational qualifications	1	5.3%
Difficulty of passing the pre-employment interview	2	10.5%
Total	19	100%

Table 3.3 Present Employment Status

Table 3.3 shows the present employment status of the 135 respondents who are currently employed. It can be seen that 37% of the respondents are with regular or permanent employment status followed by temporary status with 14% and casual with 6.7%.

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Regular/Permanent	50	37%
Casual	9	6.7%
Temporary	19	14%
Self-employed	16	12%
Contractual	41	30.3%
Total	135	100%

Table 3.4 Industry Classification of Company

Table 3.4 depicts the industry classification of the 135 employed respondents. The top 3 industry classifications are wholesale/trade (38.5%), government (24.4%); and banking and finance 20.7%. Some of the respondents are connected with the major shopping centers in the city like Al-nor Mall, City Mall, South Seas Complex and Puregolds.

On the other hand, some of them are connected in money remittance companies like Palawan, M Lhuiller, and RD pawnshop.

Industry Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Wholesale/Trade	52	38.5%
Government	33	24.4%
Banking and Finance	28	20.7%
Education	8	6%
Healthcare	5	4%
Business Process Outsourcing	2	1.4%
Travel/Tourism	6	4%
Manufacturing	1	1%
	135	100%

Table 3.5 Place of Present Work

Table 3.5 shows the place of their present work. As depicted in the table, majority of the currently employed respondents are working in the Philippines particularly in Region XII.

Place of Present Work	Frequency	Percentage
Local	130	96.3%
Abroad	5	3.7%
Total	135	100%

Table 3.6 First job after college

Table 3.6 provides data whether is it the first job of the respondents after college or not. As can be gleaned from the table, more than half of the respondents stated that their current job is not their first job after college while the other half answered that it is their first job after graduation.

First Job	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	61	45.2%
No	74	54.8%
Total	135	100%

Table 3.7 Reasons for staying the job

Table 3.7 presents the different reasons of the respondents for staying their current job. The top reasons provided by the respondents are the salaries and benefits that they are receiving from their job. Followed by the career challenge, they considered their current job as challenging and it motivates them to stay in their job. Some other reasons are related to the course or program of study and related to special skill.

Reasons	Frequency
Salaries and benefits	47
Career challenge	35
Related to special skill	19
Related to course or program of study	20
Proximity of residence	8
Peer influence	5
Family influence	13

Table 3.8 Relationship of the course to the first job

Table 3.8 provides information whether the first job of the respondents are related to their degree course. It shows that 63.7% of them answered that their first job is related to their degree. However, 36.3% of them responded that their first course is not related to their degree. Some even answered that they were employed in the Department of

Education (DepEd), Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP), Philippine National Police (PNP) after completing Bachelor of Science in Education and passing the examination for the BFP and PNP.

Relatedness of the Course	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	86	63.7%
No	49	36.3%
Total	135	100%

Table 3.9 Sources of Job Opportunities

Table 3.9 depicts the sources of job opportunities. It is clearly shown that the top sources for job opportunities are the recommendation from someone they have known and as walk-in applicants with 38.5% and 32.5% respectively. On the other hand, the least sources for job opportunities are job fair and response to an advertisement.

Sources	Frequency	Percentage
Response to an advertisement	4	3.0
As walk-in applicant	44	32.5
Recommended by someone	52	38.5
Information from friends	26	19.3
Family business	4	3.0
Job Fair or Public Employment Service Office (PESO)	5	3.7
Total	135	100

Table 4. Extent to which the curricular program contributed to the development of the graduates’ skills

Table 4 shows the extent of the curricular program in the development of graduates’ skills in terms of communication, human relations, leadership and problem solving. As depicted, the curricular program contributed to the development of communication skills, human relation skills, leadership skills, and problem solving skills of the respondents. Under the communication skills, the respondents can express ideas in clear and logical manner with the mean of 5.857 and list objectivity to gain understanding of the ideas of others with the mean of 5.877. For the human relation skills, respondents exhibit cooperative and supportive relations with others. Moreover, under the leadership skills, respondents agreed that they motivate, mobilize and inspire people to move toward the goals of the organization with the mean of 6.0. And lastly for the problem solving skills, the respondents agreed that they evaluate action for making future decisions with the mean 6.0.

Communication Skills	Mean	Std Deviation	Description
I express ideas in clear and logical manner.	5.857	1.1960	Agree
I use various forms and styles of written communication.	5.539	1.3192	Agree
I use grammatically correct language and vocabulary	5.481	1.2588	Agree
I list with objectivity to gain understanding of the ideas of others.	5.877	1.2171	Agree
Human Relations Skills	Mean	Std Deviation	Description
I demonstrate effective social behavior in a variety of setting and under different circumstances.	5.877	1.1566	Agree
I respond to the needs of colleagues in the workplace.	5.929	1.2788	Agree
I apply effective conflict resolution skills.	5.792	1.1641	Agree
I foster professional relationships with people in the workplace.	6.058	1.2059	Agree
I exhibit cooperative and supportive relations with others.	6.117	1.1601	Strongly Agree
Leadership Skills	Mean	Std Deviation	Description
I stimulate collaborative efforts with colleagues in the workplace.	5.955	1.1338	Agree
I motivate, mobilize and inspire people to move toward the goals of the organization	6.000	1.1660	Agree
I organize and coordinate people and tasks to achieve the	5.968	1.2389	Agree

organization goals.			
I facilitate effective implementation of programs of the departments/school/organization.	5.669	1.2938	Agree
I maintain self-control in the midst of stressful encounters with group members.	5.968	1.1794	Agree
I take responsibility and risks in making decisions.	5.929	1.2213	Agree
Problem Solving Skills	Mean	Std Deviation	Description
I identify the underlying issues in a problem.	5.818	1.1229	Agree
I examine alternative solutions and strategies to make an informed decision on the problem.	5.903	1.1130	Agree
I develop a clear plan to solve the problem.	5.929	1.1032	Agree
I evaluate action for making future decision.	6.013	1.1143	Agree

VI. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of Findings and Conclusion

1. Majority of the respondents are single with 84.4%. Moreover, more than half of the respondents are female with 63%. And in terms of their age, 40.9 percent belongs to the age bracket of 24-26.
2. Almost all of the respondents were graduates of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management with 94.8%. The respondents' year of graduation varies from year 2012-2019. The common reasons of the respondents were affordable tuition fee, prospect for better employment, school location, and availability of course offering in CCSPC. Almost all of the respondents did not continue professional higher education and did not pass any professional examination.
3. Majority of the respondents have been employed with 87.7% while the 12.3% accounts for graduates who have never been employed after graduation. However, the common reasons for unemployment are lack of work experience, few job vacancies, and difficulty of passing the pre-employment interview. Of the employed respondents, one-third of them are in a regular or permanent employment status. Moreover, they are commonly connected with these industry classifications: wholesale/trade, government, and banking and finance. Majority of them are working in the Cotabato City. More than half of the employed respondents stated that their current job is actually their first job after graduation and the common reasons for staying on their job are the salaries and benefit; career challenge; and relatedness of their work to the course or program of study and relatedness to their special skills. The most common source of job opportunity is the recommendation of someone they have known.
4. The curricular program contributed to the development of communication skills, human relation skills, leadership skills, and problem solving skills of the respondents. Under the communication skills, the respondents can express ideas in clear and logical manner with the mean of 5.857 and list objectivity to gain understanding of the ideas of others with the mean of 5.877. For the human relation skills, respondents exhibit cooperative and supportive relations with others. Moreover, under the leadership skills, respondents agreed that they motivate, mobilize and inspire people to move toward the goals of the organization with the mean of 6.0. And lastly for the problem solving skills, the respondents agreed that they evaluate action for making future decisions with the mean 6.0.

Recommendations

1. It is strongly recommended that the students of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration should be exposed to different activities to develop their confidence, personality and flexibility.
2. It is recommended also that the graduating students should be given ample time to experience pre-employment recruitment and selection process such as examinations and mock interviews.
3. It is recommended that the faculty members handling core professional subjects should be well trained on the different employment demands of the major establishments in the city.

4. It is recommended also that the College of Business and Public Administration should organize a review classes to prepare the students for the Professional Civil Service Examination.
5. It is also recommended that the College of Business and Public Administration should develop linkages and support system to help the graduates who are establishing their own businesses.
6. It is recommended to continuously benchmark with other universities to ensure competitiveness of the curricular offering.

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